

Random mutational induction and selection of high yielding strain of *Brevibacterium roseum* for L-threonine production

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The objective of this study was to develop a new auxotrophic mutant of *Brevibacterium roseum* from a wild strain to examine its potency for L-threonine production. A high L-threonine producing strain *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 was developed from a wild strain *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 by subsequent mutagenic treatments with EMS and UV irradiations respectively. *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 was treated with EMS solution, the auxotrophic mutants isolated show varied pattern of extracellular accumulation of L-amino acids. Sixty four auxotrophic strains were isolated out of which only thirty four excreted 1.0 to 3.7 mg/ml L-threonine and all of them require biotin and thiamine-HCl for their growth and production. Other mutants lost their excretion capacity in subsequent fermentation trials. Further mutations with UV irradiations resulted in the isolation of ninety three auxotrophic mutants out of which only nineteen excreted L-threonine higher than the parent strain. *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 excreted 6.4 mg/ml L-threonine in the fermentation broth.

Keywords: *Brevibacterium roseum*, fermentation, L-threonine, UV irradiations, EMS.

Introduction

Among the twenty proteinogenic amino acids, L-threonine belongs to essential amino acids group, used as a food supplement to improve its nutritional value as well as a flavoring agent¹. It is also registered as antiseptic, hair conditioning, hair waving or straightening; also as pharmaceutical grade in veterinary medicines². As per European Union (EU) commission, L-threonine seems to be the second most limiting amino acid after L-lysine in pig and the third most limiting amino acid in poultry birds after sulfur containing amino acids³. Considering its large demand in food and pharmaceutical industries, continuous efforts have been made to improve its production. The mutants generated by induced mutation or genetic manipulation are selected as producers due to their fast growth rates and well known pharmacological characteristics⁴.

Huang (1961) investigated two auxotrophic mutants of *Escherichia coli* for L-threonine production⁵. L-Threonine producing α -amino β -hydroxy valeric acid resistant mutant of

Escherichia coli was developed from *E. coli* K-12 with a frequency of 3×10^{-5} ⁶. Kase *et al.* (1971) treated fifteen bacterial strains with Ultra Violet light or NTG to develop auxotrophic mutants and screened them for L-threonine production⁷. Okamoto and Ikeda (2000) used an L-methionine auxotrophic mutant of *Escherichia coli* for L-threonine fermentation in large scale⁸. Recently, with the advancement of molecular biology, DNA scaffolding system was used to develop an improved strain of *Escherichia coli* for L-threonine production⁹. Wang *et al.* (2014) applied combined feeding strategies using recombinant *Escherichia coli* TRFC for L-threonine production¹⁰. Lee *et al.* (2018) examined *E. coli* MT201 developed from *E. coli* K-12 for L-threonine production by controlling sequential C/N ratios during the course of fermentation¹¹.

The present investigation was undertaken in order to develop a high L-threonine yielding auxotrophic mutant from a wild strain *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 by random mutation using Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS) and Ultra Violet (UV) irradiations as mutagens followed by selection.

Materials and methods

Microorganism: *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 isolated from North Bengal soil, was used in this study. The strain was maintained on Nutrient Agar Medium. Sub culturing was carried out once in every three weeks and the culture was stored at 4°C.

The following media were used:

Complete Medium (CM): It was composed of: glucose, 1%; peptone, 0.5%; beef extract, 0.3%; yeast extract, 0.1% and pH was adjusted to 7.0 (before sterilization).

Medium for L-threonine production: It contained: glucose, 10%; urea, 0.8%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.025%; yeast extract, 0.2% and pH was adjusted to 7.0 (before sterilization).

Minimal Medium (MM): It contains: glucose, 2%; urea, 0.2%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.025%; biotin, 0.5 µg/ml and pH was adjusted to 7.0 (before sterilization).

Treatment with Ethyl Methane Sulfonate (EMS): Cell suspension (1 ml containing 10⁸ cells) was added to 9 ml EMS solution of different concentrations (61.4 mM, 48.3 mM and 36.3 mM). After incubation (periods are given in Table 1). 1 ml sample was diluted in water in each case. The diluted bacterial cells were then plated on CD agar medium and kept at 30°C for 2 days to develop discrete colonies. After proper growth, the colonies were transferred to yeast agar slant and stored at 4°C.

Treatment with UV irradiations: 2 ml of bacterial suspension containing 10⁸ cells/ml were taken in a petri dish (5 cm diameter) and exposed to UV irradiations from a distance of 12 cm for different periods of time (Table 2). The source of radiation was Hanovia germicidal lamp (15 Watt). The treated bacterial cells were incubated at 30°C for 48 h and selected colonies were transferred to yeast extract agar slants and stored at 4°C.

The enzyme assay: The bacterial cells were incubated at 28°C for 72 h in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask containing 150 ml growth medium. The cells were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm and washed twice with chilled 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.0) followed by suspension in 10 ml of the same buffer containing lysozyme. Then it was centrifuged at 25,000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was used for enzyme assay. The total protein was assayed by the method of Bradford¹². Aspartate kinase assay was done by the method

of Bachi and Cohen¹³. The Homoserine dehydrogenase assay was done by the method of Kase and Nakayama¹⁴. Homoserine kinase activity was measured by the method of Thete *et al.* (1974)¹⁵. The phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase was assayed by the method of Canovas and Kornberg¹⁶.

Measurement of cytosolic free amino acid pool: A sample of the broth was withdrawn from the conical flask, chilled on ice, and centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 10 min to separate cells from the supernatant. The cells sediment were washed twice with 100 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.0), and boiled for 10 min to extract amino acids. After centrifugation, the extract was analyzed for cytosolic amino acids¹⁷.

Analysis of L-threonine: Descending paper chromatography was employed for the detection of L-threonine in the fermentation broth and was run for 16 h on a Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper. Solvent system used include: n-butanol:acetic acid:water (2:1:1). The spots were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and quantitative analysis was done using colorimetric estimation method¹⁸.

Quantification of L-threonine: L-threonine in the broth was confirmed using threonine dehydrogenase method as described by Asano and Ueatrongchit (2012)¹⁹.

Statistical analysis: Data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post-hoc multiple comparison test using prism 4.0. Data were expressed as mean ± SEM, where n=6.

All the chemicals used in this study were AR grade and manufactured by Mark. Borosil glass goods and deionized doubled distilled water was used throughout the study.

Results and discussion

Effect of EMS: A comparative study has been conducted on the survival of the bacterium, *Brevibacterium roseum* X1. EMS solution at a concentration of 61.4 mM had greater killing effect (Fig. 1). Maximum development of productive variant occurred when the duration of exposure to 48.3 mM was 40 min, giving the survival % of 0.6 (Fig. 2). The distribution pattern of the productive variants has been depicted in Fig. 2. The development of auxotrophic mutants of *Brevibacterium roseum* showed a maximum increase up to 40 min of exposure to 48.3 mM of EMS and then declined, while non-productive variants showed an increase pattern up to 60 min of exposure. Thus, we have isolated 64 productive variants

Fig. 1. Survival of *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 obtained by treatment with different concentrations of EMS at different time intervals in terms of logarithmic values (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n=6).

Fig. 2. Survival of the productive variants (%) with different concentrations of EMS at different time intervals (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n=6).

among which 34 excreted 1.0 to 3.7 mg/ml L-threonine and all of them required biotin and thiamine-HCl for their growth and productivity. *Brevibacterium roseum* X200 exhibited highest L-threonine productivity (3.7 mg/ml) in the broth during subsequent trials. Table 1 show different auxotrophs isolated

in this study and their amino acid accumulation patterns.

The parent microorganism *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 excreted only 0.8 mg/ml L-threonine in the fermentation broth after 72 h of incubation in shake flask culture. A number of them showed parent pattern (23.5%), where as only 26.5%

Table 1. Relation between nutritional requirements of auxotrophic mutants obtained by treatment of *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 with EMS and their amino acid accumulation

EMS (mM)	Exposure time (min)	Total No. of auxotroph	Extracellular amino acid pattern				Requirements			<i>r</i>
			L-Threonine			Others	Yeast extract	L-Amino acids	Vitamins	
			Similar to parents	Less than parents	More than parents					
61.4	10	3	1	2	–	4	1	2	1	1
	20	2	–	–	1	1	1	–	1	1
	30	2	1	1	–	–	–	–	–	1
	40	1	–	–	1	2	1	1	1	1
	50	4	–	1	–	1	1	1	1	1
	60	3	–	–	–	–	–	1	1	1
48.3	10	6	–	–	1	–	–	1	1	2
	20	2	1	–	–	–	–	1	1	1
	30	2	–	1	–	4	–	2	–	1
	40	1	2	4	1	–	2	1	–	1
	50	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	1	1
	60	2	–	1	–	1	–	–	1	2
36.3	10	6	1	2	2	–	1	–	2	1
	20	4	–	1	1	2	–	–	1	1
	30	11	1	2	–	1	2	–	4	4
	40	3	–	1	–	1	1	1	1	–
	50	4	1	1	1	1	1	–	–	11
	60	7	–	1	1	–	1	1	1	2

r = Spontaneous reversion × 10³.

showed less than parents and 50% showed more than parent pattern of L-threonine accumulation. L-glutamic acid, L-lysine, L-methionine and L-isoleucine were found to be excreted by other mutants (Table 1).

Effect of UV irradiations: The highest L-threonine producer *Brevibacterium roseum* X200 was then treated with UV irradiations (15 Watt) for different time intervals (Table 2). The scoring of survivor and the productive variants has been shown in Fig. 3. Complete inactivation of the cells was resulted in 60 min. Productive variants increased up to 40 min of the treatment and then declined gradually. About 93 auxotrophic mutants were isolated among which only 19 excreted L-threonine higher than the parent strain (*Brevibacterium roseum* X200). Table 2 shows extracellular accumulation after different periods of UV irradiations. *Brevibacterium roseum* X600, developed on 40 min exposure to UV irradiations, excreted maximum L-threonine in the fermentation broth (6.4 mg/ml).

Assay of regulatory enzymes in both *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 and *Brevibacterium roseum* X600: Fig. 4 and Fig.

5 illustrated the expression of regulatory enzymes in both *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 and *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 in a comparative manner. Assay revealed that the expression of these enzymes in the mutant strain was significantly ($p < 0.001$) depressed compared to the regulatory strain. The depressed enzymes were less sensitive to product mediated feedback inhibition.

Analysis of cytosolic free amino acids pool: As data suggested, the expression of regulatory enzymes were considerably depressed in the mutant, we can assume that the intracellular pool of L-threonine might be far lower than the extracellular accumulation. The intracellular pool of free L-threonine was examined after 72 h of incubation and revealed that it is almost one tenth of the extracellular concentrations (result not shown). No L-aspartate in the free state was detected as an inhibitory molecule for this biosynthesis.

Growth pattern study in presence of L-threonine: Lubin *et al.* (1960) reported that the mutants that have lost the ability to accumulate different amino acids in the broth were unable to transport those amino acids²⁰. Considering the fact, we

Fig. 3. The scoring of the survivor obtained by UV treatments (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n=6).

Table 2. Relation between nutritional requirements of auxotrophic mutants obtained on exposure to UV irradiations of the mutant *Brevibacterium roseum* X200 and their amino acid accumulation

Periods of exposure of UV irradiations (min)	Total No. of auxotrophs isolated	Extracellular amino acid pattern				Other amino acids	Reuirements			r
		L-Threonine			Yeast extract		amino acids	Vitamins		
		Similar to parents	More than parents	Less than parents						
10	11	2	7	2	2	2	1	11	2	
20	17	6	10	1	1	4	2	11	1	
30	24	16	6	2	4	3	1	1	1	
40	30	11	9	10	4	1	4	2	2	
50	7	2	2	3	3	1	1	1	1	
60	4	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

r = Spontaneous reversion×10³.

were intended to examine whether or not any existence of alternate L-threonine transport systems in the mutant. To explore this possibility we examined L-threonine transport in the mutant. This could easily be examined from phenotypic growth pattern of the mutant as amino acid transport defective mutants exhibited high requirement of that particular amino acid in appropriate auxotrophic condition^{20,21}. For this purpose, the growth pattern of this mutant in presence of different concentrations (10–50 µg/ml) of L-threonine was studied. But in presence of L-threonine in the growth medium, the bacterial growth pattern did not alter, suggesting thereby, L-threonine high yielding strain *Brevibacterium*

roseum X600 had been originally defective in L-threonine transport system.

In fermentation technology, the productivity of a desired metabolite in terms of its final titer is the most crucial determinant. In this present investigation, bacterial growth and L-threonine production ceased immediately after biotin was depleted (data not shown), suggesting that, it is a biotin auxotrophic mutant. The enzyme assay also depicted that high L-threonine yielding strain *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 was highly depressed with respect to three regulatory enzymes involved in microbial biosynthesis of L-threonine led to higher productivity for L-threonine.

Fig. 4. Activities of regulatory enzymes for L-threonine biosynthesis in both *Brevibacterium roseum* X1 and *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n=6).

Fig. 5. Percentage of inhibition of regulatory enzymes of L-threonine biosynthesis in presence of 20 mM L-threonine (Values were expressed as mean±SEM, where n=6).

Metabolic control of L-amino acid over production has been extensively studied in *Corynebacterium glutamicum*^{15,22-24}. Multiple rounds of mutational treatments of

Escherichia coli led to the development of an efficient L-threonine producing strain KY10935, an L-methionine auxotroph which could accumulate 100g/L L-threonine after 7 h of incu-

bation²⁵. Recombinant *Escherichia coli* B3996 was used for L-threonine fermentation and subsequently recycling the bacterial biomass²⁶. A new recombinant of *Escherichia coli* TRFC was evaluated using combined feeding strategy of pseudo exponential feeding and glucose-stat feeding for L-threonine production. This investigation provides a tool for large scale production of L-threonine¹. In this study we have seen that the parent strain produced only 0.8 mg/ml L-threonine. Mutagenic treatment of this strain with EMS developed another mutant *Brevibacterium roseum* X200 which produced even only 3.7 mg/ml L-threonine. But further mutagenic induction with UV irradiations led to the development of a biotin auxotroph, high L-threonine yielding mutant *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 which accumulated more higher amount of L-threonine (6.4 mg/ml) in subsequent fermentation trial. The auxotrophic mutant strain *Brevibacterium roseum* X600 described here could be used in the large scale industrial production of L-threonine.

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